

Understanding and Overcoming Limitations of Automated Test Generation

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I. MOTIVATION

The scale and complexity of software render manual testing an expensive and error-prone task. Search-Based Software Testing (SBST) has emerged to generate tests automatically [1], [2]. Using meta-heuristic search algorithms, SBST tools explore the input space of programs to maximise code coverage. Recently, Large Language Models (LLMs) have been integrated into SBST tools to improve their performance [3]–[9].

Despite these advancements, state-of-the-art tools and their extensions do not achieve 100% coverage. In fact, the achieved coverage is heavily influenced by the subject under test. For example, the coverage values achieved by PYNGUIN [2], [10], a test generation tool for Python, vary considerably across different datasets (see Table I): While CODAMOSA [6]—one of many extensions of PYNGUIN—achieved 91.8% coverage on a general dataset, performance on machine learning libraries [11] or projects using C-extensions [12] is lower (38.6% and 39.6%, respectively). Even if test generation tools achieve high coverage, there is room for improvement regarding other metrics, such as mutation score, bug coverage, and bug-finding capabilities [4], [13], [14]. Achieving high-quality test suites across diverse datasets has many open challenges.

We have laid the first foundations by overcoming known limitations of test generation (see Fig. 1), such as missing type information [14], instability of test generation [12], and missing information on input constraints [11]. The goal of this thesis is to understand and overcome limitations of search-based and LLM-based test generation. We will use Python and PYNGUIN to evaluate our approaches, which are designed to generalise to other languages and tools.

II. TEST GENERATION

Current research in test generation focuses on four categories:

- Property-Based Testing** tools, such as HYPOTHESIS [15], [16], allow developers to define properties and strategies for data generation, but they remain semi-automated.
- Symbolic Execution** explores program paths systematically using symbolic inputs [17] and has been successfully applied via Dynamic Symbolic Execution [7], [18], though it often struggles with the path explosion problem.
- Search-Based Software Testing (SBST)** applies evolutionary algorithms, such as DynaMOSA [19], to optimise test cases according to a defined fitness function [20]–[22].

Figure 1: Limitations and enhancements of test generation.

Table I: Final mean branch coverage of tests generated by PYNGUIN and extensions for different datasets

Source	# Modules	Branch Coverage	
		Pynguin	Extension
Lukaszczuk and Fraser, 2022 [2]	118	68.0 %	—
Lukaszczuk et al., 2023 [13]	163	71.6 %	—
Lemieux et al., 2023 [6]	486	18.4 %	91.8 %
Yang et al., 2024 [4]	486	48.8 %	64.1 %
Ryan et al., 2024 [7]	897*	64 %	66 %
Pizzorno et al., 2024 [5]	425	33.6 %	49.2 %
Krodinger et al., 2025 [14]	669	67.7 %	71.0 %
Krodinger et al., 2025 [11]	165	33.4 %	38.6 %
Berg, Krodinger, et al., 2026 [12]	1648	23.3 %	39.6 %

* Measured in methods rather than modules.

4. Large Language Models (LLMs) have been used in recent research to produce human-like test cases and overcome algorithmic limitations [3]–[5], [23], [24].

PYNGUIN [2], [10] is a state-of-the-art test-generation framework for Python that incorporates multiple SBST strategies, including DynaMOSA [19] and feedback-directed random generation [25], but also various hybrid and LLM-based approaches [6], [7]. PYNGUIN aims to achieve high code coverage by analysing the Subject Under Test (SUT) and identifying functions and methods of classes to target. It then uses search-based algorithms—which excel at optimising for code coverage—to generate high-coverage test cases and combines them with LLMs—which excel at reasoning tasks—to overcome coverage plateaus [5], [6], [8], e.g., by constructing complex objects [4] or by generating stronger assertions [3].

III. IDEAS AND PROGRESS

Limitations of test generation have been studied before [26], but not yet for untyped languages or LLM-enhanced approaches, which have their own challenges. To systematically build a failure taxonomy, we plan to apply established methods for qualitative coding [27]. Starting from an existing taxonomy,

we will iteratively label the collected failure data and organise the resulting failure labels into meaningful (sub-)categories to identify relationships between different failure causes.

The resulting taxonomy may follow the established RIPR (Reachability, Infection, Propagation, Revealability) model [28] to categorise why test generation fails to detect a fault. Code might not be covered (Reachability) because the test generation tool crashed, indicating bugs or fundamental limitations [12]. Alternatively, the tool might fail to create valid inputs (e.g., complex objects) or fail to set up a suitable precondition state. Even if the fault location is reached, the state might not be corrupted (Infection), and if it is, the corrupt state might not lead to an observable failure (Propagation), or the test oracle might be too weak to detect the failure (Revealability). Each of these categories may have multiple subcategories.

Manually labelling test generation failures is time-consuming and difficult to scale. We therefore plan to use LLMs to support this process. To systematically identify tool limitations, we will execute test generation tools multiple times per subject to account for randomness. From these runs, we collect all uncovered code, and undetected faults. To provide the LLM with focused diagnostic information, we isolate the relevant context for each failure: for tool crashes, we extract the execution stack traces; for coverage and mutation failures, we isolate and minimise the generated test cases that are closest to the target [29]. Finally, we leverage LLM reasoning to support labelling the data. Manually labelled subsets of the data will serve as ground truth to evaluate the LLM’s performance.

This approach can be used for SBST and LLM-enhanced test generation. LLMs may reason correctly in post-processing, but fail to provide a solution during the search process. For example, an LLM might fail to generate suitable inputs for a function call due to hallucinations, but later reason that the approach failed because no suitable inputs were generated.

To categorise existing limitations on real-world data, we plan not only to evaluate branch coverage and mutation score but also the fault detection capabilities on real bugs. Existing Python datasets focus on bugs from versions older than Python 3.10 [30]–[34], but PYNGUIN supports only Python 3.10 to Python 3.14 because it relies on bytecode instrumentation to measure code coverage. The Python bytecode changes between major releases, and thus PYNGUIN must be adapted for each new version. Instead of adding older, now outdated, Python versions to PYNGUIN, we plan to create a dataset of more recent Python bugs. By combining the dataset and the LLM supported categorisation, we investigate:

RQ1: *What are the limitations of automated test generation?*

Some known limitations of test generation (Fig. 1) are:

- (1) **Type Information.** In dynamically typed programming languages, test generators suffer from the lack of type information. This inhibits test generators, which heavily rely on information about parameters of functions to select suitable arguments when constructing test cases [14].
- (2) **C-Extensions.** Testing subjects that use C code via Foreign Function Interfaces for performance reasons might raise exceptions that bypass the exception handling of the calling

language and cause the test generation to fail. This limits the applicability of automated testing tools [12].

- (3) **Complex Inputs.** Certain domains, such as machine learning libraries, impose strict input constraints involving complex data structures. Generation tools are not aware of these constraints and create non-compliant inputs [11].

Completed Work. Initial results from our published work show that we overcame these limitations (Fig. 1) by:

- (i) introducing **Type Tracing**, which extracts type-related information during execution and refines the available type information, thereby allowing for better test inputs [14],
- (ii) adding **Subprocess-Execution**, which executes generated tests in an isolated subprocess and prevents crashes from halting test generation, enabling bug detection [12], and
- (iii) leveraging **API Constraints**, mined from documentation, to generate compliant test inputs [11].

These approaches serve as a first step towards answering:

RQ2: *To what degree does the mitigation of limitations enhance automated test generation?*

- (i) **Type Tracing** has a positive influence on the resulting coverage and can improve upon developer-provided type hints, yielding additional gains in branch coverage [14].
- (ii) **Subprocess-Execution** allows automated testing of up to 56.5% more modules and has discovered 213 unique crash causes, revealing 32 previously unknown faults [12].
- (iii) Using **API Constraints** achieves up to 63.9% higher code coverage for modules that impose constraints [11].

Table I shows the achieved coverage gains, which indicate that further limitations remain to be overcome.

Planned Work. We will use the insights from RQ1 not only to understand limitations of test generation, but also to develop approaches to overcome those limitations. Evaluating these newly developed approaches will then allow us to fully answer RQ2. Whenever we overcome a limitation, we enhance the underlying testing tool with the new approach, broadening the applicability of automated test generation.

Evaluation. To answer RQ1, we will create a taxonomy of limitations. For RQ2, we evaluate the effectiveness of our approaches by comparing them against the default configurations. We measure and compare branch coverage, coverage over time, mutation score, bug coverage, and fault detection capability. We use the new dataset and existing datasets [2], [6] as baselines. As test generation is non-deterministic, we run each generation multiple times and report the mean values. We use the Mann-Whitney U-test [35] ($\alpha = 0.05$) to compare configurations across modules and the Vargha and Delaney effect size \hat{A}_{12} [36] to quantify overall differences. These metrics do not assume a specific data distribution, are in line with recommendations for assessing randomised algorithms [37], and were used in previous work [2], [6], [8], [11]–[14], [38].

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